

The Universal Fluid Theory

Abstract -

Galactic Vortex Rotations and Gravity

Spacial Tension and Internal Pressure

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Acknowledgements

The current models of gravity, such as Einstein's General Theory of Relativity and Newtonian Gravity, although brilliant and revolutionary in their own right, hold significant issues and gaping holes within their assumptions of gravity, such as galactic rotation speeds and the accelerating expansion of the universe. The most recent solutions to these issues have been to "patch them" through assumed exotic particles such as dark matter, and explain the mysteries of the universe's accelerated expansion through dark energy. The issue with these solutions lies in the simple fact these are not solutions at all – they are persistent attempts to fix unfixable theories. Modern scientists have become so grounded in Einstein's work that many choose not to innovate – but to improve, to extended the original theories in order to explain the unexplained. This attempt, although noble, has led to numerous issues and overall, a large lack of progress. Dark matter, nor dark energy, has been discovered, observed, or studied by scientists, which leads to the simple conclusion that they do not exist. The Universal Fluid Theory aims to re-invent gravity through a dynamic fluid universe instead of relying on Einstein's fabric spacetime curvature, and simultaneously tackle the biggest issues known to modern science, being; singularities, dark matter, dark energy and galactic rotations. So far it matches all current observations that Einstein's General Relativity predicts while fixing the flaws in his theory, all without relying on spacetime curvature whatsoever.

Einstein's Theory of General Relativity proposes that spacetime acts as a geometric construct that can be curved and distorted under the influence of mass and energy, which then influences matter to follow geodesic paths which we observe as "gravity" (Einstein, 1915). However, this theory, while groundbreaking, held various issues, such as failing to predict the speed of galactic rotations and the expansion of the universe as previously mentioned. These gaping flaws in Einstein's Theory were decided to be the result of unobserved and unexplained phenomenon,

which led to the creation of dark matter and dark energy. Dark matter was proposed as an invisible sort of matter that does not directly interact with electromagnetic radiation, but still distorts spacetime, which would explain the far larger galactic rotations observed versus those that were previously predicted (Rubin and Ford 1970). Dark matter is still heavily explored today, with it being considered the next great mystery that will advance science once it is solved and finally discovered. Furthermore, dark energy was created in order to explain the mysterious accelerating expansion of the universe observed by the Doppler effect, which Einstein's model could not predict (Perlmutter et al 1999; Riess et al 1998). Fortunately for Einstein's theory, the cosmological constant was introduced in order to fix this issue, but it ultimately raised more questions than answers that would leave scientists baffled in how to solve them for what so far has been an indefinite amount of time, mainly being the actual reason behind their expansion. Both dark energy and dark matter have been studied for decades, with scientists pursuing theories such as MOND (Modified Newtonian Gravity) that although noble in their attempts to solve the underlying issues of gravity and dark energy, still completely fall apart in many areas such as gravitational lensing and relativity. MOND is a great example of how we are currently trying to "fix" gravity. It is able to correctly predict the speed at which galactic rotations operate, but simultaneously fails to look at the bigger picture as a whole and thus is thwarted in explaining numerous other phenomena. Other notable theories attempting to solve gravity without using dark matter or dark energy include; Tensor Vector Scalar (TeVeS), Emergent Gravity, High Order Gravity Theories and many, many more. Unfortunately, each of these theories always fall back on dark matter or dark energy, always requiring one of two mysterious phenomena in order to fully function. One can notice that each of these theories always focus on one aspect of the problem while falling flat in explaining the other. It is with my full understanding that modern scientists have been too busy working within existing theories, attempting to fix and patch them instead of innovatively coming up with their own theories. This is what leads to a decline in scientific progress, we as a society are teaching millions to focus on one theory, rather than for the millions to have one unique individual theory for their own. An attempt to stray away from this monotonous exercise of fixing and reworking failing theories is what has led me to invent The Universal Fluid Theory. The Universal Fluid Theory aims to fix the issues by unifying all concepts such as dark matter, dark energy as well as gravity as the effects of one fluid – that of which is space itself.

If one considers the "fabric" of spacetime to be not a static plane, but instead acting as a fluid, then one will find that ideas such as gravity and dark energy come easily as mere resultant effects of this fluid's behaviour. At small scales, I propose that gravity is the result of normal matter displacing space itself, which would inadvertently lead to pressure gradients acting upon the matter. The pressure gradients would then "guide" objects around this area of large displacement, resulting in the phenomena we know as "gravity". At small scales, this would effectively boil down to Newtonian gravity, being calculated as $G \frac{M_1 m_2}{r^2}$, where gravitational force is proportional to the masses of two objects divided by the distance squared, all multiplied

by the gravitational constant (G). As well as this equation works for gravity on small scales, it completely fails as distances significantly increase, with Newtonian Gravity predicting a far greater drop off in gravitational strength than observed. Furthermore, it fails in predicting the bending of light at extreme scales such as in close proximity to black holes, as well as the speed of galactic rotations and mercury's orbit. These failures require a completely new fluid interpretation of gravity in order to solve these issues and provide logical, predictable solutions. Firstly, in order to validate this theory, a formula derived from fluid mechanics that can successfully match Einstein's General Relativity at small scales is necessary in order to explain gravity as the result of a pressure driven mechanism and match mercury's orbit as well as other minor inconsistencies found in Newtonian Gravity. The following equation uses fluid mechanics with pressure gradients to successfully remove observational deviations -

$$\Delta\theta_{\text{UFT}} = \frac{6\pi GM}{c^2 a(1 - e^2)} + \frac{\alpha P}{a^n(1 - e^2)}$$

And the values -

. α (Space Fluid Strength) - 2.38×10^{18}

P (Space Fluid Background Pressure) - 1×10^{-6}

N (Exponent) - 1.87

When using this formula as an alternative to General Relativity one can observe that it produces practically identical results, yet with a completely different model of the universe that relies on fluid mechanics as opposed to spacetime curvature. This equation not only accurately predicts the precession of all orbits in the solar system, but also other solar systems as well, which is a strong indication of its accuracy. The first term allows for basic precession caused by mass and distance, and is similar to GR's formula but instead is rooted in fluid mechanics. The second term is added to adjust the precession based on the pressure gradients of space fluid, which adds the missing 43 arcseconds in Mercury's orbit. When these two terms are combined, they are able to correctly predict the precession of planetary bodies in our and other solar systems. However, as important as being able to predict planetary precessions is, this equation is not the final step in unlocking the mystery of gravity. Galactic rotations are currently the biggest issue in GR and other models of gravity, with nobody being able to properly predict galactic rotations without dark matter or without compromising other rotations. Unlike other models of gravity, this issue of gravity declining too steeply when compared to observed phenomenon such as galactic rotations can be explained in The Universal Fluid Theory as a result of the rotation of space itself in a vortex motion, which explains the steady, flat nature of the rotations. The idea of a fluid forming a vortex naturally makes sense at larger scales in terms due to the large-scale pressure gradients conserving angular momentum and being strong enough to kickstart a spiral of space motion, and this idea further helps to disprove the existence of dark matter. This theory would

allow for a logical explanation in why galactic rotations appear so flat but only at large scales – the strength of pressure gradients is allowing vortices to naturally form and maintain rotation. In order to validate this interpretation of galactic rotations without dark matter, we must rely upon the Navier Stokes Equations concerning the equation for the velocity of vortices, seen here as -

$$v = \frac{kM_{\text{baryonic}}^{1/n}}{2\pi r}$$

Where the velocity of a vortex is equivalent to the constant K (The Shorrock Constant) multiplied by the baryonic mass of the galaxy to the power of one divided by n, all divided by two multiplied by pi multiplied by the distance between the centre of the galaxy and the point at which the velocity is being measured. This equation has so far been tested on a total of nine unique galaxies, with the Milky Way being excluded due to the potential unreliable nature of our observational limits due to being located within the galaxy itself. The results appear to be promising if not potentially groundbreaking, with many galaxies showing >1% error, and only a few galaxies showing deviations, which I firmly believe is due to the observational limits in our technology and methodology, combined with minor secondary effects, rather than the equation being fundamentally flawed. The values for the tested galaxies appear as followed -

Galaxy	Distance from Centre (kpc)	Baryonic Mass (Solar Mass)	Observed Velocity (m/s)	Predicted Velocity (m/s)	Percentage Error
NGC 3198	10	1 x 10 ¹⁰	150000	149807	0.13
NGC 5055	15	5 x 10 ¹⁰	220000	215314	2.13
NGC 2403	10	8 x 10 ⁹	135000	134932	0.05
NGC 7331	14	6 x 10 ¹⁰	245000	238437	2.69
NGC 3521	12	2.5 x 10 ¹⁰	200000	193536	3.23
NGC 925	7	3.7 x 10 ⁹	110000	134423	12.55
NGC 2841	25	2.2 x 10 ¹¹	310000	262242	12.56
NGC 7793	6	1.5 x 10 ⁹	90000	101523	11.8
NGC 2903	12	3 x 10 ¹⁰	185000	182051	1.6

The majority of results show that this vortex galactic rotation theory, when mathematically applied as formula, hold extremely similar values to observed values, with the only real deviations being less than 13% in galaxy NGC 925 and NGC 2841, and less than 12% in NGC 7793. The Universal Fluid Theory clearly has a promising solution to galactic rotations if the Shorrock Constant K (Currently 2.497 x 10²⁶) and the empirical exponent n (3.981) are further refined, and if potential secondary effects are later accounted for within the formula, assuming the errors are not merely due to observational issues. This theory and its mathematical evidence

are vital for removing the long-standing mystery of dark matter once and for all, and furthering our modern perspective on gravity far more than has ever been previously thought possible.

Similar to dark matter, dark energy is also a major issue within the scientific community, with many modern science institutions attempting to resolve this unexplainable phenomenon yet to no avail. Dark energy, as previously mentioned, is what I would consider an ad hoc solution to the accelerating expansion of the universe, with no current fully working or justifiable explanation. Einstein's original solution to dark energy was known as the "Cosmological Constant", which was added into his theory of the universe in order to explain the accelerating expansion of the universe, and currently supports the Λ CDM's working theories. However, this constant, although somewhat explaining the expansion, was not only ludicrously off from correctly predicting vacuum energy, but also held the same Achilles heel most modern theories on dark energy hold – why. This simple word, why, seems to have eluded even Einstein himself, with no scientist even today able to explain the reasoning behind this accelerating expansion of the universe. What is causing it? Why does it happen? These are the questions that modern science does not possess the answers to, which is *why* The Universal Fluid Theory is vital for explaining not just the how – but the reasoning and logic behind it. This theory proposes that the resulting expansion of the universe accelerating from the big bang has no ties or links to exotic energy or particles, but is instead merely another side effect resulting from the fluid of space's behaviour. If we are correct in the assumption that space acts like a fluid, then would it not make sense that space itself would have an attraction or cohesion to itself, also known as surface tension, or as I would like to coin it "Spacial Tension". Despite logical assumptions, after computing a functioning equation, one must come to the conclusion that the outward expanding space would actually increase in "Spacial Tension", leading to space attract itself more as distance increases instead of less, however the universe seems to keep accelerating in its motion instead of slowing down. This leads to the conclusion that the momentum of acceleration overpowers spacial tension, meaning it is only relevant at the beginning of the universe and slowly becomes obsolete, allowing for the expansion to accelerate rapidly, powered by internal pressure expanding the universe outwards into true space (what I am calling a pure vacuum). This naturally explains the accelerating expansion of the universe without dark energy while simultaneously maintaining logical consistency within the theory using fluid mechanics. This idea replaces dark energy and may provide a better understanding to modern physicists of how our universe itself functions, with instead of it being a 4D fabric that mysteriously expands, the universe instead is a 3D fluid like sphere, expanding outwards at an accelerating rate due to its own internal pressure pushing it outwards. The idea of the universe's expansion relying on surface tension and internal pressure links to fluid mechanics and could be mathematically validated using the formulas

$$H(z) = H_0 \sqrt{P_s + \gamma z - \frac{\sigma_0}{(1 + \lambda_{\text{tension}} z^2)} + \epsilon(1 + z)^n}$$

$$P_s = 1 + \beta \ln(1 + z) + \delta(1 + z)^2$$

And the parameters:

H (Hubble Constant) - 70km/s/Mpc

Γ (Linear Growth) - 5.65

B (Pressure Strength) - -4.5

δ (Pressure Influence) - 0.15

σ_0 (Initial Surface Tension) - 0.29

λ tension (Surface Tension Fade) - 0.03

ϵ (Final Growth Correction) - 0.15

n (Final Growth Exponent) - 3

When using the above equation and substituting in said parameters, it can be observed that the formula correctly predicts the expansion of the universe within <1% accuracy for the majority of values, only slightly deviating up to 5% at the very lowest redshift values. I believe with certainty that this equation gives The Universal Fluid Theory a large amount of validation considering its accuracy derived from fluid mechanics, and it could potentially help to change astronomy as we know it if further tested. In this equation, $H(z)$ (the expansion rate of the universe at said redshift z) is equal to the Hubble constant multiplied by the square root of $P_s + \Gamma z - \frac{\sigma_0}{(1 + \lambda \text{tension} z^2)} + \epsilon(1 + z)^2$. Unlike models such as Λ CDM where a mysterious “dark energy” drives the expansion of the universe, P_s represents the internal pressure of the universe acting outwards to expand into pure space, which is grounded in fluid mechanics and requires no unknown ad hoc solutions to fully explain the universe’s expansion such as the cosmological constant that falls back on dark energy. When deriving internal pressure, the first term 1 ensures that there will always be a baseline pressure even today (where $z = 0$). The term $\ln(1 + z)$ is a logarithmic pressure adjustment added to allow pressure to gradually fade instead of sharply changing, which is then added to the final term $\delta(1+z)^2$ which is a quadratic growth that applies at high redshift in order to allow for strong pressure that drops off as redshift decreases in the aging universe. When combining these three terms, a suitable internal pressure is created that successfully explains the expansion of the universe dependent on its age, from the very beginnings at high pressures to the very end with low internal pressure. When trying to understand the full equation that successfully describes the expansion of the universe, internal pressure (P_s) is one small part of the equation. The Hubble Constant is the first term of the

equation, and is used to represent baseline expansion rate at $z = 0$. Furthermore, the term Γz is used to ensure smooth early expansion rates and to align with current observations. The term

$\frac{\sigma_0}{(1+\lambda_{tension}Z^2)}$ is subtracted from the expansion rate in order to account for the resistance of surface tension pulling space back on itself. σ_0 is the initial surface tension which is divided by the surface tension fade plus one (to ensure baseline tension) and then multiplied by Z squared. This squaring of high redshift (z) is crucial order to introduce weak spacial tension in the early universe, and allow it to grow as the universe expands. The final term of the equation is $E(1+z)^2$, which is vital for late term acceleration, using the final growth correction ϵ multiplied by 1 (the baseline) added to z (redshift) to the power of the final growth exponent (n), which allows for late-stage expansion to be controlled by this rapidly increasing term. This overall equation is successful in explaining the expansion of the universe while staying physically valid, with roots in fluid mechanics opposed to the majority of theories which use mathematics that either; don't fit, or have no real physical explanation. If The Universal Fluid Theory is able to make further successful predictions in terms of the universe's expansion, it may become a true contender to Einstein's General Relativity and help to eliminate dark matter once and for all.

Blackholes are one of the major glaring issues in Einstein's Theory of General Relativity. The theory predicts that at the centre of black holes, density is infinite and spacetime curves infinitely (Misner, Thorne and Wheeler 1973). Common sense tells us that this is impossible, after all, density is mass divided by volume, so how could density be infinite, or curvature for that matter? Infinity is often despised in the physics community as it suggests a theory is incomplete, or in this case, what I believe to be flat out wrong. Einstein said that gravitational lensing (the curvature of light around supermassive objects) is the result of spacetime itself curving and thus light following this curved path, resulting in the effect we see near black holes and other supermassive bodies (Misner, Thorne and Wheeler, 1973). However, what if we consider space to be a fluid like we previously have in this theory, and return to the idea of gravity being caused by pressure gradients. Would these pressure gradients, at extreme scales, not create flows so strong that perhaps light gets caught in these "currents", and moves with space, similarly to how Einstein's General Relativity uses the curvature of spacetime? As intriguing as this idea is, it would need to have mathematical evidence that matches observations with extreme accuracy, which can be seen below as the formula

$$\theta_{\text{UFT}} = \frac{4GM}{c^2b} \left(1 - \frac{\gamma P_0}{\rho} + \xi e^{-\xi \frac{GM}{c^2b}} \right)$$

With the following values -

Θ UFT (Light Deflection Angle) -

G (Gravitational Constant) -

C (Speed of Light) - 3×10^8

B (Galaxy Cluster Impact Parameter) - $1 \times 10^{21} \text{m}$

B (Black Hole Impact Parameter) - $1 \times 10^{10} \text{m}$

P_0 (Background Pressure of Space) - 1×10^{-6}

Γ (Fluid Compression Parameter) - 0.5

P (Space Fluid Density) - 1×10^{-5}

Ξ (Exponential Correction Factor) - 0.05

When using this formula, it can be observed that the effects of gravitational lensing are perfectly reproduced at all scales, such as in galaxy clusters as well as black holes. This is extremely promising mathematical evidence for The Universal Fluid Theory, as it suggests that a fluid-based model of space is valid, which could lead to major changes in the physics world if further validated. The first term, $\frac{4GM}{c^2b}$ comes from the original Newtonian bending of light in weak gravitational fields, which is useful but not the only term required in order to fully explain gravitational lensing. This first term is multiplied by the second term, $(1 - \frac{\gamma P_0}{p})$ which represents how space resists compression when influenced by supermassive objects such as galaxy clusters. It is derived from fluid mechanics with respect to pressure gradients, and acts as a multiplier that decreases lensing based on the resistance to compression of space itself (assuming space acts as a dynamic compressible fluid). This second term is then added to the third and final term

$\xi e^{-\xi \frac{GM}{c^2b}}$ which is used to suppress gravitational lensing at extreme scales such as blackholes in order to avoid overly large curvature of light. It is an exponential decay function that incorporates the Schwarzschild radius and naturally suppresses bending as distances become increasingly small between light and supermassive objects, while still allowing them to be strong enough to cause the curvature of light. This final equation is extremely successful in predicting gravitational lensing, matching Einstein's General Relativity within 0.15% at the most deviations. Unlike General Relativity however, this theory removes the need for singularities with infinite density, and further removes the need for infinite spacetime curvature, overcoming one of Einstein's biggest flaws in his theory, while keeping the same accurate results purely from existing fluid mechanics. In The Universal Fluid Theory, the centres of blackholes are not infinitely dense points, but instead an extremely dense core of matter that causes extreme

pressure gradients around it, allowing for even light to curve under the extreme flow of pressure. Given that this theory focuses mainly on gravity and its fluid – like effects, the topic of black hole cores and their properties should be left for further research, assuming The Universal Fluid Theory is correct in its assumptions.

The Universal Fluid Theory has numerous implications assuming a fluid – like universe opposed to Einstein’s 4D spacetime fabric. The first major and most obvious implication of this theory is that dark matter and dark energy simply do not exist. The equations and mathematical proof shown throughout this paper point towards the idea of gravity working without a need for any invisible mysterious substances or energies, and all observations can merely be explained as the result of a fluid – like universe and its many properties. I believe that scientists will most likely continue searching for dark matter / energy for decades to come, and they will show up empty handed. Furthermore, this theory also states that singularities are no longer needed, with the centres of black holes being replaced with ultra dense but finite in density cores, that create strong enough pressure gradients to warp light. In terms of galactic rotations, they are predicted to be much higher than Einstein’s General Relativity predicts, which can be tested by applying the gravitational vortex formula to even more galaxies than tested so far and comparing the observed results. Results may deviate slightly due to secondary effects or observational limits; however, The Universal Fluid Theory still should accurately gauge their velocity in rotation. Apart from galactic rotations and the expansion of the universe, TUFT should align with GR’s predictions through planetary orbits and most other gravitational effects. This also includes time dilation although the mechanisms causing said dilation of time may be further expanded on in a secondary paper assuming this primary paper is not outright disproven.

In conclusion, The Universal Fluid Theory is an alternative gravity model to Einstein’s General Relativity that aims to reproduce the same working results while also fixing the issues of galactic rotations, explaining the expansion of the universe (without dark matter and dark energy), explaining the hierarchy problem (as a consequence of pressure driven effects being much weaker than direct forces) and many other issues within our current understanding of physics as a whole. If this theory is further tested and holds under scrutiny then it could hopefully hold the potential to replace General Relativity as a new way of looking at the universe and how it functions not as a 4D static plane, but as a fluid – like 3D sphere expanding into a void.

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Acknowledgements -

First and foremost, I would like to say that I, Harris Shorrock, am the sole creator of The Universal Fluid Theory (Also nicknamed The Universal Soup Theory or TUFT for short) and the ideas as well as overall theory are completely my own creations. I originally had the idea of a better alternative to General Relativity January 6th 2025 and decided to pursue my idea the following days. At the time I did not think it would have any credibility – in fact – I believed it would almost immediately hold logical flaws or some sort of disprovable weakness, yet so far it has held under scrutiny. I originally published the first rough idea of my theory on Zendo however it was vastly different from the current model – including differences such as; incomplete and GR reliant mathematics, a reliance on dark matter (simply renamed dark fluid) and many other flaws.

Rebecca Taylor and Simon Richards are both scientists at CERN who, although primarily focused on particle physics, inspired me to pursue my theory with their support and motivated me to grow my theory to what it is now. Whether this theory holds future validation or not, I am very grateful for their help.

I do not know whether my theory will turn out to be a neat proposal or a completely new model of gravity, but what I do know is that curiosity and motivation have led me along this brilliant path of innovating and trying to change our understanding of physics for the better. I believe it is Isaac Newton who said that he stood on the shoulders of giants. If this is true, then I am overlooking a mountain range, because the tremendous amount of support and resources available to me have majorly helped in the development of this theory.

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